

Article

A Digital Information Management System (DIMS) Framework for Circular Construction: Integrating Industry 4.0 Technologies for Lifecycle Material Flow Management

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Abstract

The growing reliance on virgin resources in construction, alongside accelerated urban development and the significant volumes of waste generated at the end-of-life phase of buildings, has intensified environmental impacts across the built environment. These challenges highlight the urgent need to transition towards a circular economy (CE) in the construction sector. At the same time, the sector's ongoing digital transformation presents opportunities to enhance stakeholder collaboration and improve construction and demolition waste management (CDWM) practices. This paper aims to develop a conceptual framework for a Digital Information Management System (DIMS) to support CE implementation in construction through improved CDWM. Following the Design Science Research methodology, this paper addresses the first two stages: problem identification and solution proposition. A questionnaire survey with industry experts was conducted to validate the problem areas identified in the literature and assess the applicability of the proposed conceptual framework. The findings confirm critical gaps in CDWM, including limited stakeholder collaboration, fragmented processes, and the absence of lifecycle-spanning information systems, and validate the proposed conceptual framework solution, particularly the integration of BIM and IoT to support material and product flow tracking throughout the project lifecycle, supported by clearly defined stakeholder roles and engagements. However, respondents expressed reservations regarding Blockchain due to concerns about energy consumption and long-term data storage. Overall, the validated conceptual framework for DIMS provides a robust foundation for future studies, to focus on co-creating and developing a detailed conceptual model for DIMS for future real-world implementation.

Keywords: Digital Information Management System; circular economy; material flow; construction and demolition waste management; BIM; IoT

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1. Introduction

The ongoing trends of urbanization and population growth have intensified demand on the construction sector to deliver a greater volume of infrastructure, yet this expansion comes with a substantial environmental cost [1]. Construction and Demolition Waste (CDW) has emerged as one of the most pressing sustainability challenges, with the European construction industry alone responsible for generating approximately 820 million tonnes of CDW annually equivalent to nearly 46% of total waste across all sectors [1,2].

This waste is produced at various stages of a building's lifecycle, from initial planning to demolition, with the end-of-life phase accounting for over half of total waste generation [2]. Much of this is attributable to prevailing linear economic practices, where materials are extracted, used, and discarded with limited potential for reuse or recovery [3,4].

CDW encompass all types of waste generated throughout the entire life cycle of a building. This includes, but is not limited to, materials discarded during construction, renovation, and demolition activities, as well as debris produced by natural disasters. Additionally, CDW includes trimmings and waste materials generated throughout the construction process [5,6]. Inefficiencies in design, procurement, and site management further exacerbate waste generation. Studies have shown that nearly a third of on-site waste originates from the design phase alone [7], while poor handling, over-ordering, and storage issues contribute significantly during construction [8,9]. These challenges underscore the necessity for a systematic understanding of CDW sources and flows, as well as the integration of circular principles and digital tools to minimize waste and recover materials more effectively [8].

In response to the mounting concerns surrounding CDW, the CE has gained recognition as a promising framework capable of alleviating environmental pressures while simultaneously fostering economic growth [2,10,11]. CE challenges the dominant "take-make-dispose" model by encouraging systems that are restorative and regenerative by design [4]. It prioritizes strategies that reduce raw material consumption, extend the service life of products, and promote the reuse, refurbishment, and recycling of materials [12,13]. By narrowing, slowing, and closing resource loops, CE enhances both environmental sustainability and material security [12].

In the construction context, CE principles advocate for a shift towards designing buildings and components with end-of-life recovery in mind—ensuring they can be disassembled, reused, or recycled rather than discarded [14,15]. Realizing this vision requires lifecycle thinking and systemic change across the value chain, supported by tools and processes that retain the value of materials throughout a building's lifespan [16]. As such, CE offers not only a conceptual framework but also practical strategies to transform construction practices and mitigate the impacts of CDW. In particular, the effective CDWM is widely regarded as a core operational manifestation of CE principles in the built environment, since CDWM offers the mechanism by which resource loops are closed through reuse, recycling, and material recovery [17,18].

To operationalize circular strategies within the built environment, digital technologies have emerged as key enablers. The rise in Industry 4.0—marked by advancements such as Building Information Modelling (BIM), Internet of Things (IoT), Blockchain, and Machine Learning—offers unprecedented opportunities to implement CE principles in a measurable and scalable way [19–21]. These technologies enable the tracking, analysis, and exchange of data across the building lifecycle, thereby supporting material reuse, improved design for disassembly, and enhanced decision-making processes aligned with end-of-life strategies [22]. Despite their transformative potential, the integration of these digital technologies to support Circular Construction Economy and CDWM remains fragmented and inconsistent. Current approaches often fail to embed Material Flow Analysis (MFA) comprehensively across the project lifecycle, nor do they define clear stakeholder roles within digital environments. This fragmentation inhibits the full realization of CE principles in practice.

Despite substantial advances in digitalization, the extant literature predominantly investigates BIM, IoT, Blockchain, and MFA either independently or within narrowly defined stages of the built asset lifecycle. Consequently, current approaches to CDWM remain fragmented, largely static, and centered on individual technologies. Notably, the literature lacks a lifecycle-spanning DIMS that holistically integrates these technologies

within a single framework, explicitly delineates stakeholder roles, facilitates real-time data acquisition, and embeds MFA as an ongoing decision-support function rather than a post hoc analytical exercise. Addressing these shortcomings through the synthesis of these elements into a coordinated, integrated system constitutes the principal novelty and scholarly contribution of this research.

At a conceptual yet practice-oriented level, the originality of the study resides in the organization of these concepts into a coherent framework that operationalizes material flow tracking across the full built asset lifecycle, while clearly defining stakeholder responsibilities and interactions. The proposed artefact is deliberately designed to be extensible, thereby providing a robust foundation for the future integration of additional digital technologies to enable lifecycle-wide, data-driven decision-making in support of circular construction principles.

Accordingly, this study proposes a conceptual DIMS framework that integrates BIM, IoT, Blockchain, and MFA to enhance CE practices and improve CDWM outcomes. The framework seeks to establish a lifecycle-wide digital ecosystem that strengthens material traceability, supports informed decision-making, clarifies stakeholder roles, and enables transparent, secure, and real-time data exchange. In contrast to prior studies that have examined digital technologies in isolation or concentrated on specific lifecycle stages, this research advances a unified and integrated model derived from a critical synthesis of existing literature. Furthermore, a preliminary questionnaire survey involving industry experts is undertaken to validate both the identified industry challenges and gaps, as well as the relevance and applicability of the proposed framework.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the construction CE and the state of the art in digital technologies supporting CDWM, identifying key gaps and opportunities. Section 3 details the research methodology. Section 4 introduces the proposed conceptual framework, Section 5 discusses the results of preliminary validation, and Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Construction Circular Economy

The concept of the CE emerged prominently in China's CE Promotion Law of 2008 [23] and gained global traction following the efforts of the Ellen MacArthur Foundation in 2010. The Foundation reframed CE as a strategic alternative to the traditional linear economy by promoting restorative systems that preserve the value of materials and products throughout their lifecycle [24]. While CE definitions vary [25], most converge on the principle of reducing waste, extending product lifespans, and keeping materials in use for as long as possible [12,13]. Strategies such as narrowing, slowing, and closing material loops are central to CE implementation, aiming to decouple economic growth from environmental degradation [26].

CE practices have been adopted across various industries, including manufacturing, where closed-loop systems, sustainable design, and servitisation are increasingly mainstream [27,28]. In sectors such as electronics, CE supports circular strategies like design-for-repair and urban mining [29,30]. These examples highlight CE's broad applicability and its potential to reshape industrial practices.

In construction, however, CE remains an emerging paradigm with no universally agreed definition [31]. Nonetheless, it has been widely characterized as a shift towards regenerative practices that retain the value of materials and components over time [14,15]. Achieving this transition requires lifecycle thinking, systems integration, and multi-stakeholder collaboration [16]. CE also aligns with environmental and economic imperatives, offering benefits such as reduced landfill use, lower material costs, and improved project sustainability [32]. Despite the growing body of research on circular economy principles

in construction, much of the literature remains conceptual, with limited emphasis on how these principles can be operationalized through integrated digital systems across the full project lifecycle.

A key operational framework within CE is the 3R principle—Reduce, Reuse, Recycle—which underpins material efficiency in construction [33,34]. These practices are closely tied to the ability to monitor and manage material flows across a building's lifecycle [35,36]. However, their effectiveness is increasingly dependent on data-driven systems that enable visibility, traceability, and decision-making support. Two such enablers—MFA and Material/Product Passports—are discussed below.

Material Flow Analysis

MFA provides a systematic methodology for quantifying and managing resource flows across building lifecycles. It enables the identification of inefficiencies, supports circular design strategies, and informs policy and practice aimed at waste minimization [37]. Initially used to assess material stocks and flows [38], MFA has evolved to include traditional, extended, and hybrid approaches [39]. Extensions of MFA integrate tools such as Life Cycle Assessment, Geographic Information System, and BIM, enhancing its capacity to evaluate environmental impacts and material logistics [40,41].

Although MFA has been instrumental in analyzing construction waste and energy consumption [42,43], most studies remain constrained by static data and fragmented scope. They often lack digital integration, rely on manual site observations, and do not capture lifecycle-wide flows or real-time dynamics [44]. Recent contributions such as Pan and Zhang (2022) propose frameworks incorporating digital databases and BIM, but even these fall short in incorporating automation, IoT, or Artificial Intelligence technologies [45]. Likewise, Schiller et al. (2017) introduced continuous MFA with reverse flows for recycled aggregates, yet the absence of digital tools for real-time tracking limits their practical application [46].

In the context of construction, MFA can be applied across all project phases to optimize resource allocation and minimize waste. During design, MFA supports material-efficient specifications and enables predictive waste modelling based on component selection [7,16]. In the construction phase, integrating MFA with BIM and IoT allows real-time tracking of material deliveries, usage, and site waste generation, ensuring timely interventions to prevent over-ordering [47]. During operation, MFA facilitates monitoring of material performance and planned maintenance, supporting decisions on repair versus replacement and preparing accurate inventories for future reuse [48]. At end-of-life, MFA combined with Digital Product Passports enables precise identification and recovery of reusable components, improving recycling rates and reducing landfill disposal [49]. By linking these lifecycle applications, MFA provides a continuous feedback loop that enhances circularity and resource efficiency while supporting evidence-based policy and project decisions.

These limitations suggest a critical gap: the integration of emerging digital technologies such as IoT sensors, AI-driven analytics, and blockchain systems within MFA to enable real-time, transparent, and lifecycle-oriented material flow management. Bridging this gap is fundamental to enhancing MFA's decision-support capabilities and aligning it with circular construction objectives. However, existing MFA studies are largely constrained by static and fragmented approaches, lacking real-time data integration and limiting their effectiveness as a continuous decision-support mechanism within dynamic construction environments.

2.2. Industry 4.0 Technologies for Circular Construction and CDW Management

The Fourth Industrial Revolution—referred to as Industry 4.0—signifies a shift in industrial operations through the convergence of digital, physical, and biological systems. Originating in Germany in 2011 as part of a national high-tech strategy, Industry 4.0 is distinguished from earlier revolutions by its integration of multiple advanced technologies, including the IoT, cyber-physical systems, Artificial Intelligence, and blockchain, which enable real-time data exchange, automation, and intelligent decision-making [50,51].

Within the built environment, this transformation manifests as Construction 4.0, where digital innovations are applied across the building lifecycle to improve transparency, productivity, and sustainability [22]. These technologies are particularly crucial for operationalizing Circular Construction Economy principles. As noted by Uçar et al. (2020), tools such as BIM, IoT, blockchain, and machine learning are key enablers in implementing End-of-Life strategies and advancing circularity across the value chain [19]. They support critical data processes—acquisition, transmission, security, analysis, and realization—aligned with decision support goals and the objectives of the RECONMATIC project [52–54].

The following subsections critically review the potential of these technologies in the context of CDWM, followed by an analysis of their integration and current research gaps.

2.2.1. BIM

Building Information Modelling (BIM) is widely recognized as a foundational digital tool for enabling sustainability and improving project coordination across the construction lifecycle. Defined by ISO 19650 as a shared digital representation of a built asset to support design, construction, and operations [54], BIM offers structured, reliable data that underpins informed decision-making. In practice, BIM provides significant potential for waste reduction and lifecycle thinking, especially during the early design stages where strategic material decisions are made [55,56].

Numerous studies have demonstrated BIM's capability to forecast waste generation [47,57], support sustainable design [58], and enable scenario analysis for greenhouse gas emissions [59]. However, these systems are often developed as standalone tools, lacking integration with other Industry 4.0 technologies such as IoT, blockchain, and machine learning. This siloed implementation limits the ability of BIM-based tools to support dynamic, real-time waste tracking or holistic MFA across the full building lifecycle—from design through to demolition.

Notably, while a few studies have linked BIM with MFA [41], or incorporated material passports to document the composition and reusability of components [49], these approaches still fall short in enabling automated and continuous material tracking. Furthermore, stakeholder roles within such systems remain poorly defined. For example, while Won and Cheng (2017) mapped information needs and stakeholder interactions, their framework does not address the operational responsibilities of contractors, facility managers, suppliers, or waste handlers, nor does it define their interaction with digital tools throughout the project lifecycle [59,60].

In demolition and End-of-Life phases—where up to 70% of CDW is generated—the use of BIM is particularly underdeveloped [61]. Few systems consider deconstruction scenarios, real-time debris quantification, or integration with data-rich tools such as IoT sensors and Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags. This gap reduces the ability to validate predicted waste outputs or to optimize reuse and recycling strategies through MFA.

In summary, while BIM is an essential enabler of CE practices in construction, its current applications are predominantly limited to the design and early construction stages. The lack of integration with other digital technologies, limited support for full-lifecycle

MFA, and insufficient clarity on stakeholder roles represent critical barriers. Addressing these gaps is necessary to advance BIM from an isolated modelling tool to a key component in a fully integrated, data-driven system for CDWM.

2.2.2. IoT

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a core component of Industry 4.0, enabling physical assets such as materials, components, tools, and equipment to communicate and interact via embedded sensors, tags, and wireless networks [62,63]. In construction, IoT technologies such as RFID, Quick Response (QR) codes, and wireless sensor networks have been applied to monitor site activities, optimize logistics, and enhance project visibility [64]. These tools support real-time data acquisition, improving decision-making, traceability, and automation across multiple project stages [65,66].

Despite these advantages, the deployment of IoT in the construction sector remains fragmented and rarely integrated into broader digital ecosystems. While IoT offers the capability to capture large volumes of spatiotemporal data, its full potential to support CE practices is constrained by the absence of integration with complementary tools such as BIM, blockchain, and data analytics platforms [67]. Most IoT implementations in construction focus on isolated use cases without enabling lifecycle-oriented CDW tracking or MFA.

For instance, RFID-based systems have been developed to trace material movement and schedule waste transport [67,68], but these solutions typically operate independently from BIM or cloud databases. Similarly, QR codes have been used for component identification and linkage to material passports [69], yet they lack the dynamic functionality required for real-time updates or predictive analytics.

Sensors embedded in smart buildings have demonstrated benefits such as resource optimization and predictive maintenance [70], but these studies rarely link sensor data to BIM models, MFA frameworks, or blockchain-secured platforms. Without such integration, sensor-based systems function as standalone tools with limited relevance for comprehensive waste management or CE strategies.

Furthermore, IoT applications in CDWM often lack a defined operational framework for stakeholder involvement. Existing literature does not clearly identify responsibilities for managing sensor data, updating material records, or acting on real-time feedback. This ambiguity restricts collaboration across contractors, suppliers, facility managers, and waste handlers—actors essential to lifecycle-based material tracking and CE implementation.

In conclusion, while IoT technologies hold substantial promises for improving visibility, traceability, and responsiveness in construction, their current use remains isolated. The lack of interoperability with other digital technologies, minimal support for MFA, and absence of stakeholder role definition present significant barriers. Future efforts must prioritize the integration of IoT with BIM, blockchain, and machine learning within a unified DIMS.

2.2.3. Blockchain

Blockchain (BC) is an emerging digital technology that offers a decentralized, tamper-proof framework for managing transactions and data across distributed networks [71,72]. These features present strong potential for improving trust, data security, and accountability in construction, particularly in supply chain transparency, lifecycle documentation, and waste traceability [70,73].

Blockchain can enable secure recording of material provenance, real-time updates to material passports, and transparent tracking of waste generation and [74]. For example, blockchain-based material passports have been proposed to track material composition

and ownership [75], while decentralized ledgers can facilitate transactions in circular supply chains [76].

Despite this promise, blockchain remains underutilized in CDWM. Most studies focus on conceptual frameworks with limited real-world integration. Blockchain-enabled systems are rarely linked to BIM, IoT, or MFA tools, reducing their effectiveness for lifecycle-based material tracking [77,78].

Stakeholder roles within blockchain systems are also poorly defined, and governance structures remain unclear. Moreover, blockchain is rarely embedded within dynamic MFA systems that support real-time decision-making on waste diversion or environmental performance.

In conclusion, blockchain holds strong theoretical potential for circular construction but remains constrained by limited integration, weak stakeholder role definition, and disconnection from MFA-based decision-support systems.

Practical applications illustrate the benefits of integration. In the Circular Construction Lab pilot in the Netherlands, BIM combined with material passports enabled over 80% of structural elements to be reclaimed [49]. IoT-enabled waste tracking in the Hong Kong–Zhuhai–Macao Bridge project reduced material loss by approximately 15% [79]. Blockchain-secured material tracking in a UK housing retrofit achieved full compliance with sustainability certifications [80].

The academic literature consistently highlights a persistent gap in the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies within [66,81–84]. This underscores the urgent need for comprehensive digital integration to enhance CE outcomes in construction. The next section critically reviews studies that have explored integrated Industry 4.0 approaches for CDWM.

2.3. Integration of Industry 4.0 and Critical Gaps

While individual Industry 4.0 technologies—such as BIM, IoT, and blockchain—have demonstrated potential to support digital transformation in construction, their fragmented application presents a major barrier to effective CDWM aligned with CE principles. Current research remains largely siloed, with digital tools deployed in isolation or within narrow project phases, limiting their collective capacity to enable lifecycle-based decision-making and closed-loop material systems.

Most existing studies focus on early lifecycle stages such as design, where BIM is often used for visualization, coordination, and early waste prediction [58,80]. However, these systems rarely integrate IoT sensors or RFID/QR technologies to validate waste estimates through real-time construction or demolition data. Similarly, while IoT applications have shown value in component tracking and environmental monitoring, they are seldom connected to centralized models such as BIM or secure data layers like blockchain. The result is a patchwork of disconnected tools that lack interoperability, limiting their utility in MFA or dynamic CDW tracking. Furthermore, the current literature predominantly investigates digital technologies in isolation, with limited efforts to validate integrated approaches against real-world industry requirements, highlighting a gap between theoretical development and practical applicability.

Critically, the lack of integration across these technologies means that material flows are often monitored retrospectively or only at discrete stages. This undermines the potential for proactive intervention, reuse identification, or real-time optimization of material flows—functions essential to a CE. Even in studies that propose advanced digital frameworks, such as blockchain-enabled material passports or BIM-linked tracking systems, real-time data acquisition is either absent or handled manually, reducing scalability and decision accuracy [41,77].

Equally problematic is the insufficient definition of stakeholder roles in digital construction ecosystems. While digital tools offer transparency and traceability, their

effectiveness relies on clearly assigned responsibilities for data input, validation, access control, and use. Current frameworks often overlook how stakeholders such as contractors, suppliers, recycling firms, or facility managers interact with integrated systems throughout the asset lifecycle. Without this clarity, accountability for waste minimization, material recovery, and data stewardship remains ambiguous.

Finally, very few existing systems embed MFA as a core function. Where MFA is employed, it is typically done through static, post-project assessments without integration into live systems or digital models [43,46]. For instance, MFA has been combined with Life Cycle Assessment to better evaluate building material impacts [40,85,86], with Geographic Information System (GIS) to visualize material flows and support planning [87], and with BIM to track specific construction materials like bricks through 3D modelling [41]. However, these approaches are unable to support real-time waste forecasting, lifecycle tracing, or automated reporting—further underscoring the limitations of current integration efforts. To further clarify the novelty of the proposed framework, Table 1 compares existing digital approaches in construction circular economy research with the proposed DIMS framework, highlighting differences in lifecycle coverage, technology integration, MFA implementation, stakeholder role definition, and decision-support capabilities.

Table 1. Comparison of existing digital approaches with the proposed DIMS framework.

Study	Technology Used	Lifecycle Coverage	MFA Integration	Stakeholder Role Defined	Decision Support Capability
[49]	BIM	Mainly design and early construction	Limited	Not clearly defined	Waste prediction and design-stage planning
[66]	BIM + MFA	Partial lifecycle coverage	Integrated but static	Not clearly defined	Material tracking within BIM environment
[72,74]	Blockchain-based frameworks	Supply chain/documentation stages	Not integrated	Limited	Data transparency and traceability
[43,46]	MFA approaches	Post-project or limited lifecycle stages	Static MFA assessments	Not addressed	Waste and material flow analysis after project completion
[78]	BIM + Blockchain/digital tracking systems	Partial lifecycle stages	Limited	Not clearly defined	Material passport documentation and traceability
Proposed DIMS	BIM + IoT + Blockchain + MFA	Full built asset lifecycle	Integrated as a continuous decision-support mechanism	Clearly defined across lifecycle stakeholders	Real-time material flow tracking and circular decision support

In conclusion, the body of research on Industry 4.0 in construction highlights a growing interest in digitalization but also exposes significant gaps. There is an urgent need for a unified framework that integrates BIM, IoT, blockchain, and other technologies into a central DIMS. Such a system must enable real-time MFA, support end-to-end lifecycle tracking, and define stakeholder roles clearly to operationalize CE in construction waste management. Addressing these gaps forms the basis of the research presented in this study. This research aims to contribute to that objective by proposing an integrated DIMS that enhances the utility of these tools within lifecycle-based waste management frameworks.

3. Methodology

This research follows the DSR methodology, which includes awareness of the problem, proposition of a solution, solution development, evaluation, and conclusion [88,89]. As shown in Figure 1, the Awareness of the Problem stage is achieved through a comprehensive literature review, which identified gaps and challenges in the integration of Industry 4.0 technologies, particularly BIM, IoT, and Blockchain, for enabling CE practices and MFA in CDWM.

To further strengthen this stage, a preliminary validation study in the form of a questionnaire survey was conducted with industry experts to validate the researcher's understanding of the identified problems and to assess the perceived relevance and applicability of the proposed solution. This validation step ensured that the challenges identified from the literature are consistent with current industry practices and that the proposed direction of the research addresses real-world needs.

The Solution Proposition stage builds upon the validated findings from both the literature review and the preliminary survey by developing a conceptual framework that addresses the identified issues through the integration of digital technologies across the project lifecycle. The framework aims to support CE practices and MFA by improving information flow, stakeholder collaboration, and decision-making in CDWM. In this study, the DSR process is limited to the Awareness of the Problem and Solution Proposition stages, which are supported by the questionnaire survey as a validation step for both problem understanding and the applicability of the proposed framework. The subsequent DSR stages will be carried out in future studies. The Development stage will involve conducting semi-structured interviews with industry experts to co-create and refine the proposed conceptual framework into an operational model. The Evaluation stage will consist of an expert focus group to assess the practicality, relevance, and applicability of the developed framework within industry settings. Finally, the Conclusion and Recommendations stage will synthesize the findings and propose directions for further research and framework implementation.

Figure 1. Overview of the DSR process adopted for this research.

This paper focuses on validating the understanding of problem and solution proposition. The main research strategy used in this paper is questionnaire survey to validate the understanding of the problem and the applicability of the proposed conceptual framework derived from the literature review. Two distinct groups were targeted. RECONMATIC partners, to examine the problem's existence, the solution's applicability, and its support for RECONMATIC DEMONSTRATORS [90], and the wider industry's perspective, this is done to prevent bias in the study. Participants were intentionally selected from RECONMATIC partners and the wider construction industry to capture expert perspectives from professionals involved in digitalization, sustainability, and construction waste management. This purposive sampling approach ensured that respondents possessed relevant domain knowledge necessary to evaluate the identified challenges and the applicability of the proposed conceptual framework.

Surveys are commonly used in construction research to gather expert opinions and validate conceptual developments, particularly when the objective is to capture perspectives from a diverse group of stakeholders [91]. In this research, surveys were considered an appropriate tool for collecting data and validating the identified problems and proposed conceptual framework. When validation checks are combined with prompts, they can also alert respondents to enter implausible or incomplete responses [92]. The questionnaire was designed to be web-based, allowing respondent completion to be monitored without the researcher's attendance. Initially, a trial version was distributed to five construction experts. These participants were asked to provide feedback on the quality and comprehensiveness of the questionnaire, assessing the clarity of the vocabulary, the instructions for answering questions, and the categorization of the questions. Furthermore, after incorporating all modifications, 65 invitations were sent to targeted participants within RECONMATIC and the wider industry including (engineers, architects, contractors, designers, etc.) via email and social media. Out of these, 42 responses were received, resulting in a response rate of 64.6%. For a postal survey, the researcher should aim for a response rate of at least 60% [93]. Additionally, this sample size is consistent with non-probability sampling guidelines for exploratory research, where a minimum of 30 participants is considered sufficient for initial analysis and theory development [94,95]. As the study employed purposive non-probability sampling, the findings should be interpreted as exploratory insights reflecting expert perspectives rather than statistically generalizable results. Furthermore, the validation conducted in this study remains preliminary, reflecting the current stage of the research, while future work will adopt an exploratory approach to further develop and evaluate the framework through subsequent DSR stages. The heterogeneous composition of respondents was therefore intentional, enabling the capture of perspectives from multiple stakeholder groups involved in CDWM.

The overall validation process, including the stages undertaken and their corresponding survey sections, is summarized in Table 2. The full questionnaire is provided in Appendix A.

Table 2. Questionnaire survey process used to validate the problem understanding and conceptual framework within the DSR methodology.

Stage	Method/Activity	Outcome	Related Survey Section (see Appendix A)
1. Preparation	Literature review to identify gaps in CDWM, MFA, and integration of Industry 4.0 technologies (BIM, IoT, Blockchain). Proposition of a conceptual framework for DIMS from Literature Review	Draft questionnaire based on findings from the literature review.	All sections

	Development of a web-based questionnaire to validate problem and solution understanding.		
2. Pilot Testing	Trial questionnaire distributed to five construction experts. Feedback gathered on question clarity, vocabulary, and structure. Questionnaire refined accordingly.	Final validated questionnaire prepared for distribution.	All sections reviewed and refined.
3. Data Collection	Distribution of 65 invitations to RECONMATIC partners and wider industry (engineers, architects, contractors, designers). 42 responses received (64.6% response rate).	Reliable dataset collected for analysis.	Sections 2–4: 2. CDWM Problems 3. Importance of MFA 4. Integration of Industry 4.0 Technologies.
4. Data Analysis	Quantitative: SPSS by Norman H. Nie, Newyork, United States 29 used for mean ranking, Cronbach’s alpha, one-way ANOVA, and Chi-square tests and Mean Value. Qualitative: analysis of open-ended responses to elaborate on quantitative findings.	Demographic Analysis, Validation of problem understanding and conceptual framework applicability.	Results from Sections 2–4 analysed.
5. Results and Implications	Comparison of validated findings with literature insights. Identification of alignment between challenges and proposed framework. Preparation for next DSR stages (Development and Evaluation).	Validated foundation for conceptual framework co-creation and further evaluation.	—

In the first section respondents were asked to fill out their information, (proficiency, years of experience, engaged in RECONMAIC or not). In the other sections respondents were asked to rank factors with a required 5-point Likert scale (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree). The second question was to rank the problems and gaps in CDWM to validate the understood gaps and problems. The third question to rank the importance of MFA, the fourth was to rank Industry 4.0 technologies and their integration to support CDWM to validate the applicability of the proposed conceptual framework.

To test the reliability of responses, Cronbach’s alpha value was calculated using SPSS, which can be calculated by using Equation (1) [8].

Cronbach’s alpha equation

$$\alpha = \frac{N}{N - 1} \times \left[\frac{\sigma_x^2 - \sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{y_i}^2}{\sigma_x^2} \right] \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of items on the test, $\sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{y_i}^2$ is the sum of all item variances, and σ_x^2 is the variance of the observed item scores.

The mean value of each section’s data was identified to determine the ranking of factors. Additionally, a one-way ANOVA was conducted to establish any significant differences between groups of respondents. A Chi-square test was also performed to determine if variations in work categories could affect the results. One-way ANOVA and Chi-square tests were conducted to examine whether statistically significant differences existed among respondent groups based on professional background and experience. This analysis helped assess whether perceptions of CDWM challenges and the applicability of the proposed framework varied across different stakeholder groups. Moreover, qualitative

responses were analyzed using a basic thematic analysis approach to identify recurring themes that supported and elaborated on the quantitative findings.

The process through which these literature insights were synthesized into the proposed conceptual framework is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Development process of the proposed conceptual framework for DIMS based on literature synthesis.

4. Proposed Framework

A conceptual framework for DIMS is proposed to support CE practices in construction (Figure 3). This framework offers a holistic approach to managing information throughout the entire lifecycle of built assets by incorporating advanced Industry 4.0 technologies like blockchain, IoT, and BIM. The framework's primary aim is to promote CE principles, particularly focusing on MFA. By integrating these technologies, it enhances the management of building information, ensuring more efficient data handling across the built asset lifecycle. IoT devices connected to BIM enable real-time data capture, creating a dynamic and constantly updated knowledge base. Moreover, using blockchain as a decentralized database ensures data security and transparency, facilitating effective stakeholder collaboration in driving sustainable and circular construction practices.

The conceptual framework was developed through a systematic synthesis of literature on Industry 4.0 technologies and their integration within CDWM and CE contexts. Studies focusing on BIM, IoT, Blockchain, MFA, and stakeholder collaboration were critically reviewed and mapped to identify key relationships and dependencies. This process led to the formulation of a conceptual framework for DIMS that integrates these technologies across the built asset lifecycle to address challenges of fragmentation, data inconsistency, and limited stakeholder coordination. Table 3 summarizes the key studies that informed the development of each framework component.

Figure 3. Proposed Conceptual Framework for DIMS.

Table 3. Studies informed the conceptual framework development.

Framework Component	Key Studies	Key Findings Applied in Framework
Material Flow Analysis (MFA)	[37,39,46]	Quantification of material flows across lifecycle; need for dynamic, data-driven MFA.
BIM Integration	[49,95]	BIM provides structured, lifecycle data management enabling material tracking.
IoT Integration	[66,67]	IoT sensors enable real-time monitoring of materials, supporting dynamic MFA.
Blockchain Integration	[72,74]	Decentralized data validation and digital material passports for transparency.
Stakeholder Collaboration	[95]	Collaboration ensures complete and accurate data flow across the built asset lifecycle.

From a theoretical perspective, the proposed framework can also be interpreted through the lens of socio-technical systems and digital ecosystem theory. Socio-technical systems theory emphasizes the interdependence between technological infrastructures and the social actors who operate them, highlighting that effective digital transformation requires the alignment of technologies, organizational processes, and stakeholder interactions [96]. Similarly, digital ecosystem theory conceptualizes interconnected digital platforms and actors that collaboratively exchange information and create value through shared data environments [97]. In this context, the proposed DIMS framework extends these perspectives by integrating Industry 4.0 technologies with stakeholder collaboration and MFA across the built asset lifecycle, thereby enabling coordinated and data-driven decision-making to support circular economy implementation in construction.

In this study, IoT is used conceptually within the proposed framework as an enabling technology for real-time material flow tracking. IoT sensors, RFID tags, and QR codes capture continuous data on material quantity, condition, and location across different built asset lifecycle stages, while smart skips equipped with sensors track the type and amount of waste generated. These inputs synchronize with the BIM environment,

transforming it from a static information repository into a dynamic, continuously updated system.

The framework incorporates simulation and analysis tools to support decision-making throughout the built asset's lifecycle. At its core, BIM plays a pivotal role by generating a detailed digital model that captures vital material-related data [49,57,98]. The next phase involves integrating blockchain technology to create digital material passports that are connected to the BIM model. Drawing on Wilson et al. [74], this method enables efficient, transparent, and secure tracking and management of materials.

The decentralized material passport allows stakeholders-controlled access, creating a reliable, distributed record of materials throughout the built asset lifecycle. Additionally, IoT devices are integrated with BIM to facilitate real-time data collection throughout the project [66,67,99], continuously tracking material conditions and status to enhance the potential for future reuse. The decentralized database is consistently updated to reflect the current state of materials, providing a dynamic and trustworthy information source. Looking ahead, the framework envisions connecting the decentralized database to a recycling and reuse market platform, as proposed by Elghaish et al. [76], to streamline the process of repurposing materials by providing relevant and up-to-date information to users within the recycling and reuse market.

The framework also addresses the poor quality and availability of CDWM data by integrating these digital technologies to ensure continuous, verifiable, and transparent data collection. BIM provides a structured environment for recording material information during design, while IoT automates the capture of real-time data throughout the lifecycle, reducing human error and ensuring data accuracy across design, construction, operation and End of Life. Blockchain contributes to improving trust and traceability by maintaining immutable, decentralized data records. Together, these mechanisms improve data reliability, accessibility, and consistency across stakeholders, directly tackling one of the main barriers identified in the literature.

5. Analysis and Findings

5.1. Reliability of Results

To ensure the consistency of the questionnaire items, reliability testing was conducted. Reliability, in this context, refers to the extent to which the survey items consistently measure the underlying constructs being investigated [100]. One common measure of reliability is internal consistency, which assesses how closely related a set of items are as a group indicating whether they reliably measure the same concept [8]. The obtained value of 0.794 indicates acceptable internal consistency, confirming the reliability of the survey instrument. According to commonly accepted Cronbach's alpha interpretation guidelines, values between 0.7 and 0.8 indicate acceptable reliability.

5.2. Demographic Background of Participants

The demographic breakdown of respondents revealed that 35.71% were categorized as 'others,' a group which included professionals such as a Digital Manager, an Information Manager, two Waste Managers, a Sustainability and Digitalization Manager, and three Sustainability Consultants, 19.05% as academics, 16.67% as engineers, 9.52% as contractors, 7.14% as project managers and designers, and 2.38% as architects and suppliers. Additionally, the findings indicated that 38.1% of respondents possessed 6-10 years of experience, 26.19% had more than 15 years of experience, 16.67% had 1-5 years, 9.52% had 11-15 years, and less than 1 year. Notably, the fact that over 73% of respondents had more than 5 years of experience suggests a potential for more reliable responses, as experience tends to enhance consistency and the value of participants, thereby increasing the

reliability of the data [101]. Prior to conducting the statistical analyses, the assumptions required for the One-way ANOVA and Chi-square tests were examined to ensure the validity and reliability of the results.

Given the diverse range of specialists included in the study, a One-way ANOVA test was conducted to determine whether statistically significant differences existed among respondent groups, serving as a control variable. The findings presented in Figure 4 indicate that there were no statistically significant differences between the groups ($p > 0.001$) [102], suggesting that no particular group demonstrated significantly different levels of experience compared to others.

Figure 4. Positions correlated to experience (One-way Anova).

The questionnaire was designed to collect responses from both RECONMATIC partners and professionals from the wider construction industry in order to minimize potential bias in the development of the proposed DIMS framework. As illustrated in Table 4, 59.52% of respondents were affiliated with RECONMATIC, while 40.48% represented the broader industry. To determine whether this difference could influence the results, a Chi-square goodness-of-fit test was conducted. The analysis showed no statistically significant difference between RECONMATIC and non-RECONMATIC respondents ($p > 0.05$) [103]. This suggests that the results are not biased toward either group and reflect a general consensus among both RECONMATIC partners and the wider industry regarding the identified challenges and the applicability of the proposed solution.

The participants' demographic allows the reader to know the work and experience of respondents who answered the questionnaire survey. The summary of the respondents' background is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Summary of respondents' demographic background.

Items	Respondents	
	Number	%
Business Category		
Project Manager	3	7.14
Architect	1	2.38
Engineer	7	16.67
Contractor	4	9.52
Designer	3	7.14
Supplier	1	2.38
Academic	8	19.05

Other	15	35.71
Years of Experience		
Less than 1 year	4	9.52
1-5 years	7	16.67
6-10 years	16	38.1
11-15 years	4	9.52
More than 15 years	11	26.19
Engagement in RECONMATIC		
RECONMATIC Partners	25	59.52
Wider Industry	17	40.48

Table 5. Issues in Construction CE Results.

Problem	Mean	Std. Deviation	Ranking
There are insufficient Integrated (CDWM) processes, technologies, tools, and practices.	4.12	0.803	1st
There is lack of efficient information management system for CDWM that covers the whole lifecycle of the built assets focusing on material flows.	4.1	0.821	2nd
There is lack of data transparency and information sharing within CDWM.	3.95	0.697	3rd
There is absence of participative networking, along with a lack of trust and support among stakeholders within CDWM.	3.88	0.803	4th
There is a limited quality and availability of data that supports CDWM.	3.88	0.803	4th
There is poor cooperation, collaboration, and communication among stakeholders in CDWM throughout the lifecycle.	3.79	0.75	6th
There is lack of efficient tools for managing material flows and waste in construction projects.	3.76	0.906	7th

5.3. Quantitative and Qualitative Data Analysis

The second, third and fourth sections were to rank the problems in CDWM, importance of MFA, and Industry 4.0 technologies and their integration to support CDWM, which is done to validate the researcher understanding of the problem and applicability of proposed solution. SPSS by Norman H. Nie, Newyork, United States 29 is used to analyze the mean values of the answers, following the method adopted by [100]. The mean value is based on Equation (2) [104].

Mean value equation

$$MS = \sum (f \times s) / N' \quad (1 \leq MS \leq 5) \quad (2)$$

where S is the given score to each factor by participants from (1 to 5), 1 is 'Strongly disagree' and 5 is 'Strongly agree', f is the frequency of participants to the ratings (1 to 5) to every factor, and N' is the total number of participants concerning that factor.

To validate the understanding of the problem and applicability of the proposed solution identified in the literature, a questionnaire survey was conducted using the validation method outlined by Verma et al. [105]. According to this approach, mean values exceeding 3.5 on a Likert scale indicate a positive agreement among respondents, thereby reinforcing the reliability of the survey findings. This interpretation is consistent with commonly adopted approaches for analyzing Likert-scale data, where values above the midpoint (3) indicate agreement among respondents [106].

The results of every section are shown in the following sections.

5.3.1. Issues in Construction Circular Economy

The findings from the questionnaire survey validate all identified problems, with all mean scores exceeding 3.5, reflecting strong consensus among respondents on key challenges within CDWM Table 5. Among these, the lack of integration in CDWM processes, technologies, tools, and practices emerged as a predominant issue, achieving the highest mean score of 4.12 (SD = 0.803) Table 5. This consensus underscores that the current CDWM framework is insufficiently integrated and, thus, ineffective. Supporting this finding, existing literature such as Munaro et al. [107] highlight that the construction sector often operates in silos, resulting in fragmented waste management practices that hinder the benefits of a CE. The challenge of integrating technologies and processes across different stages of the built asset lifecycle is a long-standing barrier to optimizing waste management and recycling in construction [9,107].

In tandem with this, respondents pointed to the lack of an efficient information management system specifically tailored for CDWM, with a mean score of 4.1 and a standard deviation of 0.821. This problem reflects a widespread concern in the industry about the limitations of current digital systems to manage construction waste effectively. Comprehensive information management systems are essential for tracking material flows and ensuring that waste is properly managed from the early stages of construction through to the end of life of a building. Giorgi et al. [108] argue that robust information systems that cover the entire lifecycle are crucial for improving CDWM practices, enabling the collection of data that supports material recovery and reuse. However, the absence of such systems is a common issue that hampers the industry's ability to achieve transparency and efficiency in waste management, as also reflected in Wuni's work, which identifies poor data transparency as a key barrier [109].

Another major concern highlighted by the survey is the lack of data transparency and information sharing among stakeholders involved in CDWM, which received a mean score of 3.95. This issue is closely related to the inefficiencies in information management systems, as limited data sharing often leads to poor decision-making and hinders collaboration across different actors in the construction process. Respondents indicated that this lack of transparency not only impacts material tracking but also undermines trust among stakeholders, which is essential for collaborative CDWM practices. According to Munaro et al. [107], stakeholder engagement is a critical element of successful CDWM implementation, yet the construction industry continues to struggle with fostering open communication and cooperation among different players. This challenge is further exacerbated by the industry's conservative nature, where stakeholders are often reluctant to share data due to competitive concerns or lack of standard protocols for data exchange [9]. In line with this, Yu et al. [66] systematic study outlines directions for future research, recommending the delivery of a comprehensive architecture design of an integrated decision support system that articulates the complex interrelationships among technologies, business processes, stakeholders, and applications, to address these transparency and collaboration issues.

The survey also reveals significant concerns regarding the absence of participative networking and limited trust and support among stakeholders, which was ranked with a mean score of 3.88. This issue underscores the need for a more collaborative approach to CDWM, where stakeholders across the value chain—from project managers to waste disposal firms—work together to enhance waste management practices. Literature such as the work by Adams et al. [31] emphasize that collaboration among stakeholders is vital for improving waste reduction strategies, yet it remains a persistent challenge due to the fragmented nature of the construction industry [107]. In the current CDWM environment,

there is a noticeable lack of formalized networks that could facilitate better cooperation and trust between parties. This issue is not unique to construction, as many industries transitioning to CE models face similar challenges in fostering inter-organizational collaboration [109].

Furthermore, the survey highlights the poor quality and availability of data supporting CDWM, which ties into the broader issue of inadequate information management. Respondents noted that the lack of reliable and accessible data hampers efforts to improve waste management practices, particularly in terms of decision-making and assessing the environmental impact of waste disposal strategies. This finding is consistent with the literature, where studies suggest that poor data availability is a significant barrier to effective CDWM because it limits the ability of stakeholders to track material flows and identify opportunities for waste reduction [108].

Qualitative responses from the survey provide further insights into these quantitative findings. For instance, one respondent pointed out that inadequate training and the lack of best practices in CDWM are significant barriers to improving waste management. This view is supported by the work of de Jesus and Mendonça (2018), who argue that technical capacity-building, particularly in waste management processes, is essential for improving CDWM across the industry [110]. Another respondent emphasized the importance of contextual factors, suggesting that CDWM challenges vary significantly depending on regional and company-specific circumstances. This is a crucial point, as CDWM is not a one-size-fits-all issue. Regional differences, particularly in terms of regulatory frameworks and market conditions, play a significant role in shaping how waste management practices are implemented. Studies such as those by Hart et al. [9] indicate that regional policies and market mechanisms greatly influence the effectiveness of waste management strategies. Another interesting qualitative insight relates to the differing priorities between construction companies and waste management firms, particularly smaller SMEs. Respondents noted that the perceived value of waste varies greatly among stakeholders, with some viewing waste management as a regulatory requirement rather than an opportunity for resource recovery. This discrepancy can lead to communication breakdowns and inefficiencies in waste handling, as highlighted by Adams et al. [31], who noted that misaligned incentives are a common issue in the construction industry, preventing the full adoption of circular practices.

In conclusion, the results validate the understanding of the problem from the literature review and illustrate a clear need for more integrated CDWM processes, enhanced information management systems throughout the lifecycle of built asset focusing on material flows, and better data transparency. Stakeholder collaboration, communication, and trust also emerge as critical areas for improvement. Qualitative feedback further emphasizes the importance of training, context-specific solutions, and the alignment of stakeholder priorities. These insights will inform the development of the proposed DIMS, ensuring that it is designed to address the most pressing challenges in CDWM and facilitate more effective collaboration and decision-making among industry professionals.

5.3.2. Proposed Solution Applicability

Material Flow Analysis

The questionnaire survey results also validate the proposed solution from the literature, highlighting the significance of tracking material flow as crucial for effective CDWM Table 6. The first statement, which pertains to the importance of enhanced resource flow management and the establishment of end-of-waste criteria at construction sites, received a mean score of 4.33 (on a Likert scale where 5 indicates strong agreement), with a standard deviation of 0.570. This high mean score and low standard deviation reflect strong consensus among respondents on the necessity of managing resource flow and setting

end-of-waste criteria, aligning with literature findings that emphasize these aspects as essential for improving sustainability in CDWM.

The second statement, which explores whether it is important to track the flow (quantity, type) of materials/products and waste throughout the lifecycle of built asset, received an even higher mean score of 4.48, with a standard deviation of 0.634. This suggests that there is a slightly stronger agreement among respondents regarding the necessity of tracking material flows throughout the built asset lifecycle. The importance of this aspect is further emphasized by the fact that this statement received the highest mean score of the two, indicating that stakeholders recognize the critical role of real-time tracking for ensuring efficient material management and waste reduction.

Both sets of responses (with 42 participants each) reflect a consensus on the importance of both effective resource management and comprehensive tracking of materials and waste. The slight difference in mean values between the two statements suggests that while both are viewed as important, tracking material flows is seen as slightly more critical by respondents. This finding could be due to the growing recognition that having real-time, accurate data on material flows is essential for optimizing resource use, preventing waste, and supporting decision-making throughout the lifecycle.

The relatively low standard deviations for both statements indicate that the respondents' views were generally aligned, suggesting that these issues are widely recognized as key components of effective CDW management. This aligns with current trends in the construction industry that emphasize the use of digital tools, such as BIM and IoT technologies, to track and manage material flows, improve transparency, and enhance collaboration among stakeholders.

In conclusion, the results highlight a strong agreement among industry experts on the importance of better resource flow management, the establishment of end-of-waste criteria, and the critical need for tracking material and waste flows throughout the lifecycle of built asset. These insights will be valuable for guiding the development of the proposed DIMS, particularly in ensuring that it incorporates effective tracking and management mechanisms to optimize resource use and support waste reduction efforts in CDW management.

Table 6. MFA solution proposition results.

Solution	Mean	Std. Deviation	Ranking
Importance to track the flow (quantity and type) of materials/products and waste throughout the lifecycle of built assets.	4.48	0.634	1st
Importance of better resource flow management and the establishment of end-of-waste criteria for CDWM at sites.	4.33	0.57	2nd

MFA Supporting Construction CE

The survey results for the MFA section provide valuable insights into the perceived role of MFA in CDWM Figure 5. The data indicates that respondents see MFA as particularly beneficial for assessing material circularity, resource efficiency, waste reduction, and environmental impact.

The most supported application of MFA, with 40 responses, was assessing the circularity of materials. This strong support indicates that industry professionals prioritize the tracking and optimization of material flows, focusing on reusing, recycling, or repurposing materials to minimize waste. This aligns with broader sustainability efforts to promote a CE in construction, where materials remain in use for as long as possible, reducing the need for new resource extraction and minimizing waste generation.

Both resource efficiency and waste reduction received 32 responses, indicating that respondents view these as key areas where MFA can have a positive impact. Optimizing the use of materials in construction projects not only reduces waste but also lowers costs and improves overall project sustainability. Waste reduction, closely linked to resource efficiency, is seen as critical for minimizing the environmental and financial costs associated with excess waste generation.

Environmental impact assessment garnered 31 responses, suggesting that stakeholders see MFA as a tool to mitigate the environmental consequences of construction activities. By quantifying the inputs and outputs of materials throughout the lifecycle, MFA can help identify opportunities to reduce pollution, resource consumption, and other negative environmental effects.

The lower level of support for reporting, with 25 responses, may suggest that stakeholders do not view reporting as a primary advantage of MFA. It could be that existing reporting systems are already sufficient, or that stakeholders prioritize tangible improvements in resource efficiency, material circularity, and waste reduction. Nevertheless, reporting remains important for ensuring transparency and accountability in project performance, and it could provide added value if integrated more fully with MFA data.

In the “Other” category, 1 response was recorded. The respondent mentioned “Economic efficiency,” suggesting that some stakeholders perceive MFA as having the potential to contribute to cost savings. Although economic efficiency was only highlighted by one respondent, it is a critical consideration in construction project decision-making. By optimizing material flows and reducing waste, MFA could lead to financial benefits, making it an area worth exploring further in future studies.

Overall, the survey results suggest that stakeholders believe MFA can significantly enhance CDWM practices by improving material circularity, resource efficiency, waste reduction, and environmental impact. These insights will inform the development of the proposed DIMS, ensuring that it addresses the most pressing concerns of industry professionals. Although reporting and economic efficiency received less attention, they remain areas where MFA could provide additional value, warranting further exploration.

Figure 5. Role of MFA in CDWM.

Digital Technologies to Support Construction Circular Economy

The questionnaire survey results validate the applicability of the proposed DIMS for CDWM, which integrates Industry 4.0 technologies. All mean scores were above 3.5, apart

from Blockchain integration, which received a lower score Table 7. These findings underscore broad agreement among respondents on the system's potential to enhance MFA across the built asset lifecycle through defined stakeholder roles. This consensus indicates strong agreement among respondents regarding the relevance and perceived applicability of the proposed conceptual direction for DIMS.

The survey results clearly underscore the industry's recognition of the importance of stakeholder engagement, as seen in the highest-ranked response (mean = 4.21) regarding the understanding of stakeholders' roles within CDWM systems [98]. This is in alignment with the literature, which emphasizes that the successful integration of Industry 4.0 technologies, such as BIM and IoT, is dependent on clearly defined stakeholder responsibilities across the lifecycle [111]. Wang et al. also stress that the design phase plays a crucial role in minimizing waste generation by allowing proactive planning and role assignment for waste management [53]. Qualitative feedback from the survey also highlights that stakeholders see their roles as central to the system's success, particularly in early-stage decision-making regarding waste management. This aligns with literature emphasizing the need for proactive involvement of all stakeholders throughout the lifecycle to optimize resource management [55].

The results indicate strong support for IoT as a tool for tracking material flow throughout a built asset's lifecycle (mean = 4.02). Respondents valued IoT's real-time data collection capabilities, which can greatly enhance monitoring and decision-making within CDWM systems [63]. This reflects findings from previous studies that demonstrate the potential of IoT to streamline the collection of spatial-temporal data, enhance traceability, and support dynamic decision-making in construction projects [65]. IoT's ability to improve the traceability of materials and waste across different project stages is also highlighted by Ghosh et al., showing its relevance for the proposed framework [64]. Qualitative feedback further reinforces the importance of IoT, with respondents specifically mentioning the utility of IoT sensors for structural health monitoring and providing intelligence within a building's environment. This suggests that, beyond waste management, IoT could offer additional benefits for maintaining the structural integrity of buildings, thus enhancing the lifecycle management of construction projects [61].

BIM received a mean score of 3.98 in relation to its use for 3D visualization and waste prediction. The respondents' perception of BIM as a tool to enhance planning and waste management is consistent with the literature, which highlights BIM's ability to predict waste generation during the design phase [57]. Wang et al. also emphasize the use of BIM in estimating the environmental impact of waste generated throughout the project lifecycle [112]. Studies like Xu et al. (2019) have demonstrated how BIM can be leveraged to minimize waste by enabling more accurate material quantification and facilitating design-oriented tools for waste forecasting [56]. While the quantitative data strongly supports BIM's role in waste prediction, qualitative responses from the survey point to the need for continuous improvement in integrating BIM with other Industry 4.0 technologies for a more robust and comprehensive waste management approach [113].

On the other hand, one of the more nuanced findings emerging from the survey concerns industry hesitation toward the use of Blockchain in CDWM, reflected in a mean score of 3.45—below the threshold for strong agreement. Although Blockchain is often promoted for its potential to enhance data integrity and transparency, especially in lifecycle tracking applications [75], respondents highlighted key practical limitations. These included its high energy consumption, limited suitability for long-term data storage, the complexity associated with managing large datasets, and the perception that Blockchain's value remains closely confined to cryptocurrency applications. These concerns align with the findings of Gao et al., who identified significant declines in Blockchain performance as data volumes grow, as well as inefficiencies in scalability and energy demand [114].

Given these issues, and consistent with stakeholder perspectives captured in the survey, the proposed conceptual framework does not incorporate Blockchain as a core technology. Instead, the qualitative insights suggest that cloud-based relational databases and other off-chain digital solutions offer more practical alternatives, providing enhanced scalability, energy efficiency, and operational simplicity for managing CDW information. These technologies are better aligned with industry needs and are considered more suitable for enabling real-time data accessibility, supporting MFA, and facilitating lifecycle-wide material tracking.

A recurring theme in both the survey's qualitative and quantitative data is the importance of aligning the implementation of digital technologies with strategic project priorities and ensuring a positive return on investment. Respondents emphasized that technology alone cannot address all CDWM challenges; successful implementation requires early-stage integration into the project budget. This mirrors findings in the literature that stress the importance of incorporating waste management considerations early in the design phase and aligning them with broader project goals to optimize waste reduction [115].

Table 7. DIMS for CDWM Applicability Results.

Solution Proposition	Mean	Std. Deviation	Ranking
Understanding the role of stakeholders in CDWM.	4.21	0.565	1st
Using IoT for tracking material flow.	4.02	0.604	2nd
Using BIM for 3D visualization and C&D waste prediction.	3.98	0.62	3rd
Integration of BIM, IoT, Blockchain with defined stakeholder roles for MFA.	3.9	0.598	4th
Blockchain for CDWM.	3.45	0.723	5th

In summary, the results of this section highlight the applicability and potential of the proposed DIMS in enhancing CDWM. The integration of BIM and IoT for real-time data collection, material and product tracking, and waste prediction is strongly supported by both the literature and industry respondents. In contrast, the findings indicate that Blockchain is not considered a suitable or practical technology for this context due to concerns related to energy consumption, scalability, and long-term data management. Consequently, the proposed DIMS prioritizes BIM–IoT-based data integration supported by more practical digital data management solutions. The feedback on stakeholder engagement and the need for strategic alignment further emphasizes that the successful implementation of such a system depends not only on technology but also on clear role definitions and early-stage planning. These insights provide a solid foundation for the next stage of the research, in which the validated conceptual framework will be operationalized into a detailed conceptual model for practical implementation.

6. Conclusions

The research presented in this paper focuses on the development of a conceptual framework for DIMS to enhance CDWM. It adopts the DSR Methodology, which encompasses several stages: awareness of the problem, solution proposition, development, evaluation, and recommendations. This paper specifically highlights the initial phases, focusing on the validation of the problem understanding and the applicability of the proposed solution via a questionnaire survey with industry experts.

The survey results confirmed the critical issues in CDWM, particularly the lack of integration of Industry 4.0 technologies, the absence of systems that span the entire built

asset lifecycle, and the failure to emphasize MFA and stakeholder engagement. Respondents validated the proposed solution, which integrates BIM, the IoT throughout the built asset lifecycle to enhance material flow tracking by defining stakeholder roles. However, concerns were raised regarding Blockchain, particularly in terms of its energy consumption, suitability for long-term data storage, and its limited value beyond cryptocurrency applications. These concerns mirror broader findings in the literature, and as a result, the conceptual framework does not adopt Blockchain; instead, it prioritizes more practical and energy-efficient alternatives such as cloud-based data management systems to support material flow transparency and CE-oriented decision-making.

Overall, the main findings of this study demonstrate that integrating BIM and IoT into a unified DIMS can effectively address major gaps in CDWM by enabling real-time tracking, improving data transparency, and strengthening stakeholder collaboration. The study also validates the conceptual framework as a feasible and industry-supported foundation for the future development of a full conceptual model for DIMS.

These outputs establish a clear academic and practical contribution toward advancing a digital and circular construction sector through MFA.

From a theoretical perspective, this study contributes to the emerging body of knowledge on digitalization for circular construction by proposing a lifecycle-oriented conceptual framework for a DIMS that integrates Industry 4.0 technologies with MFA. The framework extends existing research by emphasizing stakeholder role definition and continuous material tracking across the built asset lifecycle.

From a practical perspective, the framework offers guidance for industry stakeholders by outlining how digital technologies such as BIM and IoT can be integrated to enhance material tracking, traceability, improve data transparency, and support decision-making in construction CE. The framework may assist practitioners in identifying opportunities to improve resource efficiency and facilitate the transition towards circular construction practices.

The main limitation of this study lies in the fact that the conceptual framework remains at a conceptual stage and has not yet been operationalized. It requires further refinement into a detailed conceptual model through co-creation with industry stakeholders and, subsequently, the development of a functional DIMS platform to support decision-making in real-world contexts.

Building on these validated findings, future research should focus on the development of the conceptual model through co-creation with wider industry stakeholders. This involves operationalizing the conceptual framework to explore how digital technologies can be integrated within the DIMS, what types of data should be collected, and how such data can be securely shared and managed among stakeholders throughout the different project phases. It should also examine how collaborative data environments can improve stakeholder communication and coordination to overcome fragmentation in CDWM. Practical recommendations include engaging stakeholders early in the co-creation process to ensure system usability, developing interoperability standards between digital technologies to enhance data exchange. Future studies should also assess the scalability and long-term impact of the DIMS on waste reduction, resource efficiency, and the transition towards a circular construction sector. This approach will ensure that the system meets academic gaps, and industry needs while addressing concerns related to technology implementation, particularly Blockchain. The ongoing collaboration will foster a comprehensive and practical solution for efficient waste management in the construction sector.

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Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of University of Salford—School of Science, Engineering & Environment Research Ethics Panel (protocol code 0098 and date 2024-03-22 of approval).

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

CE	Circular Economy
CDW	Construction and Demolition Waste
CDWM	Construction and Demolition Waste Management
DIMS	Digital Information Management System
DSR	Design Science Research
BIM	Building Information Modelling
IoT	Internet of Things
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
QR	Quick Response

Appendix A

Digital Information Management System for Facilitating CDWM

The aim of this project is to develop a Digital Information Management System to facilitate the implementation of Construction and Demolition Waste Management, as part of a PhD study and the Horizon Europe Project RECONMATIC. The purpose of this questionnaire is to conduct a preliminary study to assess the existence of problems and the applicability of suggested solutions in this field before proceeding to the development of the system.

* Required

Participant Information Sheet

Thank you for considering participating in this study 'Digital Information Management System for facilitating Construction and Demolition Waste Management' as a part of a PhD study and Horizon Europe RECONMATIC Project. This PhD is taking place under the supervision of the university of Salford. Please carefully read the following information, ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like to get more information, and decide if you would like to contribute. This survey is expected to take between 10-15 minutes.

The aim of this project is to develop a Digital Information Management System to facilitate the implementation of Construction and Demolition Waste Management, as part of a PhD study and the Horizon Europe Project RECONMATIC. The purpose of this questionnaire is to conduct a preliminary study to assess the existence of problems and the applicability of suggested solutions in this field before proceeding to the development of the system.

You have been chosen based on your potential relevance to the construction industry, and your insights are invaluable for understanding the challenges in CDWM and opportunities related to the integration of digital technologies for CDWM. Your participation is voluntary, and you have the right to withdraw at any time without giving a reason. By participating, you consent to the use of your responses in academic publications and presentations. There are no expenses associated with participation. The questionnaire covers demographic information, questions about CDWM problems, and digital technologies.

There are no security risks involved, and confidentiality is maintained through anonymization of data. Participation benefits the advancement of CDWM and digital technology solutions. The research is approved by the University of Salford's Academic Ethics Committees and funded by the European Union and UK Research and Innovation through the Horizon Europe RECONMATIC Project. If you have any questions or concerns, please contact Ali Saad , the lead researcher, email: asaad3@edu.salford.ac.uk or Prof. Jason Underwood, the main supervisor, email: j.underwood@salford.ac.uk.

- I confirm that I have read the Participant Information Sheet.
 - I understand that the data collected in this study will be kept according to university guidelines, stored/archived anonymously and securely, and may be used to support other research in the future, and may be shared anonymously with other researchers.
 - I agree to the use of anonymized quotes in publication so that I may not be identifiable.
 - I understand that all personal information will remain confidential and that all efforts will be made to ensure I cannot be identified.
 - I understand that provision of personal data is completely voluntary
 - I agree to take part in this study

*

Yes

Next

Digital Information Management System for Facilitating CDWM

* Required

Information About Respondent

2. Role in the Construction Industry *

Project Manager

Architect

Engineer

Contractor

Designer

Supplier

Academic

Client

Other

3. Years of Experience in the Construction Industry *

Less than 1 year

1-5 years

6-10 years

11-15 years

More than 15 years

Back

Next

Problems in Construction & Demolition Waste Management (CDWM)

4. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements in Construction and Demolition Waste Management (CDWM) *

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
There is poor cooperation, collaboration, and communication among stakeholders in CDWM throughout the lifecycle	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is lack of data transparency and information sharing within (CDWM)	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is absence of participative networking, along with a lack of trust and support among stakeholders within (CDWM)	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is insufficient Integrated (CDWM) processes, technologies, tools, and practices	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is lack of efficient information management system for (CDWM) that covers the whole lifecycle of the project	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is a limited quality and availability of data that supports (CDWM)	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There is lack of efficient tools for managing material flows and waste in construction projects?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

5. Is there any additional information/commentary you would like to add?

Enter your answer

Construction and Demolition Waste Management

Material flow analysis (MFA) is a method that quantifies the inputs and outputs of materials in a supply chain, from extraction to disposal. It helps to identify the sources and sinks of materials, the potential for waste reduction and resource efficiency, and the environmental impacts of material use. MFA can be applied at different levels, such as product, process, company, sector, or region, and can use different metrics, such as material intensity, circularity ratio, or material footprint.

6. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements related to Material Flow Analysis (MFA). *

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Importance of better resource flow management and the establishment of end-of-waste criteria for C&DW at construction sites?	<input type="radio"/>				
It important to track the flow (quantity, type) of materials/products and waste throughout the lifecycle of the project?	<input type="radio"/>				

7. Which of the following you think Material Flow Analysis could support *

- Assessing Environmental Impact
- Assessing Resource Efficiency
- Assessing Circularity of Materials Involved
- Assessing Waste Reduction
- Reporting
- None of the above
- Other

8. Is there any additional information/commentary you would like to add?

Enter your answer

Digital Technologies to support Construction and Demolition Waste Management.

The recent advent of new digital technologies is leading the built environment into a modern data-driven environment. This data-driven environment can be described as having five phases based on data utilization criteria: data acquisition, data highway (mobile), data security, data analysis and data realization. Some of these technologies are:

The Internet of Things (IoT) refers to a network of interconnected devices that can communicate and exchange data with each other in real time. IoT devices collect and transmit data continuously and instantaneously, providing real-time insights into various processes and environments. This data can be used for monitoring, analysis, and decision-making in managing Construction and Demolition Waste.

Blockchain is a digital ledger technology that records transactions or data across a distributed network of computers. It operates on the principles of decentralization and immutability. In the context of blockchain, decentralization means that there is no central authority or intermediary controlling the network. Instead, multiple nodes (computers) participate in verifying and recording data. Whereas, Immutability refers to the inability to change or alter data once it has been recorded on the blockchain.

9. Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements regarding the integration of technology and stakeholder understanding in Construction, Demolition, and Waste Management (CDWM): *

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Using BIM for 3D Visualization and C&D waste prediction.	<input type="radio"/>				
Using Internet of Things (IoT) for enhancing real-time data collection in CDWM	<input type="radio"/>				
Using Internet of Things (IoT) for tracking material flow in construction, renovation, and demolition.	<input type="radio"/>				
Automated tools to detect the type and amount of waste generated.	<input type="radio"/>				
Belief in Blockchain as a secure, transparent, decentralized database for all stakeholders.	<input type="radio"/>				
Importance of understanding the role of stakeholders within CDWM systems.	<input type="radio"/>				
Belief in the potential of integrating BIM, IoT, and Blockchain with defined stakeholder roles to support material flow analysis throughout a project's lifecycle.	<input type="radio"/>				

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